

Malware Recognition Based on Semantic Behaviors Using Machine Learning Techniques

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ABSTRACT

A tremendous number of malicious programs have posed severe and evolving security threats to operating systems and the Internet. Driven by the substantial profits behind cybercrimes, the amount of new variants of malware has experienced unprecedented growth. Malware refers to any software accessing or being installed in a system without the authorization of administrators. Various malware has been widely used for cyber-criminals to accomplish their evil intentions and goals. To combat the increasing amount and reduce the threat of malicious programs, a novel deep learning framework, which uses NLP techniques for reference, combines CNN neurons to capture the locally spatial correlations and learn from sequential long-term dependency is proposed. Hence, high-level abstractions and representations are automatically extracted for the malware classification task. The classification accuracy improves from 0.81 (best one by Random Forest) to approximately 1.0

Keywords: Clement, Malware Detection, Machine Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

A tremendous amount of malicious programs have posed severe and evolving security threats to operating systems and the Internet. Driven by the substantial profits behind cybercrimes, the amount of new variants of malware has experienced unprecedented growth. According to Panda Labs, in the 3rd quarter of 2016 alone, over 18 million new malware instances have been found, which means an average of 200,000 samples per day. To fight against the large-scale malware in the wild, it is a pressing necessity for automatic and effective malware detection and classification systems, which play significant roles in maintaining the security of operating systems and networks. However, with respect to the design of effective and efficient mechanism for malware detection and classification, there are challenges we are encountering. Many concealment techniques, such as encryption, packing, obfuscation, polymorphism and metamorphism, have been adopted by malware writers to evade detection. As the pattern matching method is still the dominant approach to detect potential malware by analyzing the disassemble code statically, which is easily defeated by conventional evasion techniques, leading to a higher request for effective malware detection approaches. Machine learning and data mining have been explored to tackle cyber security issues such as discovering unknown and unforeseen attacks, which have demonstrated effectiveness in intrusion detection and malware classification.

1.2 Overview

Malware refers to any software accessing or being installed in a system without the authorization of administrators. Various malware has been widely used for cyber-criminals to accomplish their evil intentions and goals. To combat the increasing amount and reduce the threat of malicious programs, a novel deep learning framework, which uses NLP techniques for reference, combines CNN neurons to capture the locally spatial correlations and learn from sequential long-term dependency is proposed. Hence, high-level abstractions and representations are automatically extracted for the malware classification task. The classification accuracy improves from 0.81 (best one by Random Forest) to approximately 1.0.

Fig 1: Types of Machine Learning

1.3 Objectives

The specific objectives of malware prediction can vary depending on the context and application.

- **Early detection:** The primary goal is to detect malware as early as possible, ideally before it can cause any harm. Early detection allows for prompt remediation and minimizes the potential impact on the system or network.
- **Accurate identification:** Malware prediction aims to accurately identify whether a given file, application, or network traffic contains malware. This requires developing robust algorithms that can distinguish between legitimate and malicious software with a high degree of accuracy.
- **Behavioural analysis:** Malware prediction often involves analysing the behaviour of software or network traffic to identify patterns or characteristics associated with malware. By studying the behaviour of known malware and detecting similar patterns, it becomes possible to predict the presence of new or previously unknown malware.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1 Related Works:

Several compressive reviews about the subject of Clement machine learning methods for malware recognition based on semantic behaviours have been previously presented in the literature form here are few reviews of IEEE paper, journals, thesis and books for the various approaches to go about this project.

[1] S. Choudhury and A. Bhowal, "Comparative analysis of machine learning algorithms along with classifiers for network intrusion detection", *Smart Technologies and Management for Computing Communication Controls Energy and Materials (ICSTM)*, 2015.

Intrusion detection is one of the challenging problems encountered by the modern network security industry. A network has to be continuously monitored for detecting policy violation or suspicious traffic. So an intrusion detection system needs to be developed which can monitor network for any harmful activities and generate results to the management authority. Data mining can play a massive role in the development of a system which can detect network intrusion. Data mining is a technique through which important information can be extracted from huge data repositories. In order to spot intrusion, the traffic created in the network can be broadly categorized into following two categories- normal and anomalous. In this proposed paper, several classification techniques and machine learning algorithms have been considered to categorize the network traffic. Out of the classification techniques, we have found nine suitable classifiers like BayesNet, Logistic, IBK, J48, PART, JRip, Random Tree, Random Forest and REPTree. Out of the several machine learning algorithms, we have worked on Boosting, Bagging and Blending (Stacking) and compared their accuracies as well. The comparison of these algorithms has been performed using WEKA tool and listed below according to certain performance metrics. Simulation of these classification models has been performed using 10-fold cross validation. NSL-KDD based data set has been used for this simulation in WEKA.

[2] M. J. Kang and J. W. Kang, "A novel intrusion detection method using deep neural network for in-vehicle network security", *Vehicular Technology Conference*, 2016.

Here the author proposed a novel intrusion detection technique using a deep neural network (DNN). In the proposed technique, in-vehicle network packets exchanged between electronic control units (ECU) are trained to extract low-dimensional features and used for discriminating normal and hacking packets. The features perform in high efficient and low complexity because they are generated directly from a bit stream over the network. The proposed technique monitors an exchanging packet in the vehicular network while the features are trained offline, and provides a real-time response to the attack with a significantly high detection ratio in our experiments.

[3]T. Hoppe, S. Kiltz and J. Dittmann, "Security threats to automotive can networks practical examples and selected short-term countermeasures", *Reliability Engineering and System Safety*, vol. 96, no. 1, pp. 11-25, 2011.

The IT security of automotive systems is an evolving area of research. To analyse the current situation and the potentially growing tendency of arising threats we performed several practical tests on recent automotive technology. With a focus on automotive systems based on CAN bus technology, this article summarises the results of four selected tests performed on the control systems for the window lift, warning light and airbag control system as well as the central gateway. These results are supplemented in this article by a classification of these four attack scenarios using the established CERT taxonomy and an analysis of underlying security vulnerabilities, and especially, potential safety implications.

With respect to the results of these tests, in this article further discuss two selected countermeasures to address basic weaknesses exploited in our tests. These are adaptations of intrusion detection (discussing three exemplary detection patterns) and IT-forensic measures (proposing proactive measures based on a forensic model). This article discusses both looking at the four attack scenarios introduced before, covering their capabilities and restrictions. While these *reactive* approaches are short-term measures, which could already be added to today's automotive IT architecture, long-term concepts also are shortly introduced, which are mainly *preventive* but will require a major redesign. Beneath a short overview on respective research approaches, we discuss their individual requirements, potential and restrictions.

[4]U. E. Larson, D. K. Nilsson and E. Jonsson, "An approach to specification-based attack detection for in-vehicle networks", *IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium Proceedings*, 2008

An upcoming trend for automotive manufacturers is to create seamless interaction between a vehicle and fleet management to provide remote diagnostics and firmware updates over the air. To allow this, the previously isolated in-vehicle network must be connected to an external network, and can thus be exposed to a whole new range of threats known as cyber-attacks. The authors explore the applicability of a specification-based approach to detect cyber-attacks within the in-vehicle network. We derive information to create security specifications for communication and ECU behavior from the CAN open draft standard 3.01 communication protocol and object directory sections. We also provide a set of example specifications, propose a suitable location for the attack detector, and evaluate the detection using a set of attack actions.

[5]M. Muter, A. Groll and F. C. Freiling, "A structured approach to anomaly detection for in-vehicle networks", *2010 6th International Conference on Information Assurance and Security IAS 2010*, 2010.

The complexity and connectivity of modern vehicles has constantly increased over the past years. Within the scope of this development the security risk for the in-vehicle network and its components has risen massively. Apart from threats for comfort and confidentiality, these attacks can also affect safety critical systems of the vehicle and therefore endanger the driver and other road users. Here the author proposed the introduction of anomaly detection systems to the automotive in-vehicle network is discussed. Based on properties of typical vehicular networks, like the Controller Area Network (CAN), a set of anomaly detection sensors is introduced which allow the recognition of attacks during the operation of the vehicle without causing false positives. Moreover, important design and application criteria for a vehicular attack detection system are explained and discussed.

2.2 Existing System:

To protect target systems and networks against malicious activities anomaly-based network IDS is a valuable technology. Despite the variety of anomaly-based network intrusion detection techniques described in the literature in recent years [8], anomaly detection functionalities enabled security tools are just beginning to appear, and some important problems remain to be solved. Several anomaly based techniques have been proposed but majority of those technique lacks the accuracy with which the detection method is done. The major

challenges in evaluating performance of network IDS is the unavailability of a comprehensive network based data set.

Disadvantages:

- Low accuracy.
- Cannot be scaled beyond a point.
- Higher complexities.
- Failed to consider semantic behaviors.

2.3 Proposed System:

The promise and the contribution machine learning did till today are fascinating. There are many real life applications we are using today offered by machine learning. It seems that machine learning will rule the world in coming days. The proposed system came out with a hypothesis that the challenge of identifying new attacks or zero day attacks facing by the technology enabled organizations today can be overcome using machine learning techniques. The proposed system as a supervised machine learning model that can classify unseen network traffic based on what is learnt from the seen traffic. The proposed system used both SVM and ANN learning algorithm to find the best classifier with higher accuracy and success rate. The proposed system is composed of feature selection and learning is a type of feature selection component is responsible to extract most relevant features or attributes to identify the instance to a particular group or class. The learning algorithm component builds the necessary intelligence or knowledge using the result found from the feature selection component. Using the training dataset, the model gets trained and builds its intelligence. Then the learned intelligences are applied to the testing dataset to measure the accuracy of how much the model correctly classified on unseen data.

Advantages:

- Higher accuracy.
- Can be heavily scaled.
- Low complexities.
- Considers semantic behaviors.

3. SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION

A System Requirements Specification (SRS) is a collection of composed information. The essentials must be measured, surveyed, identified with perceive the prerequisites and it contributes all the level of unpretentious components satisfactory for structure plot. Hardware and Software necessities are two sorts of system requirements used as a piece of our endeavor.

A SRS is a completed interpretation without limits reason and surroundings for the item a work in advancement. The SRS totally shows which programming work and how it will be will predict to finish. A SRS minimizes the time and cost change and attempt that should be made by the architect, remembering the final objective to fulfill their fancied destinations. A good nature of SRS allows how an application will talk with system gear, distinctive ventures and human clients in a wide arrangement of genuine circumstances.

The most usually apparent game plan of supplies described by programming application is the bodily P-C possessions, in like manner called as gear. That physical need subtle element is a social occasion of instruments for assignment change associates with programming and offers simple to utilize interface to working up the endeavor.

The structure contains the spiral and other module for the help of the execution to happen.

3.1 SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS:**❖ Hardware Requirements**

Processor : Any Processor above 500 MHz

Ram : 4GB

- Hard Disk : 250 GB.
- Input device : Standard Keyboard and Mouse.
- Output device : High Resolution Monitor.

❖ **Software Requirements**

- Operating System : Windows Family.
- Programming : Python 3.5 and related library files.

❖ **Technology Requirements:**

- Tensorflow
- Numpy
- Pandas
- Matplotlib
- Scikit – learn
- Python

3.2 System Architecture:

Architecture diagrams can help system designers and developers visualize the high-level, overall structure of their system or application for the purpose of ensuring the system meets their users' needs. They can also be used to describe patterns that are used throughout the design. It's somewhat like a blueprint that can be used as a guide for the convenience of discussing, improving, and following among a team.

Fig 2: System Architecture

4.2 Flowchart:

A flowchart is simply a graphical representation of steps. It shows steps in sequential order and is widely used in presenting the flow of algorithms, workflow or processes. Typically, a flowchart shows the steps as boxes of various kinds, and their order by connecting them with arrows. It originated from computer science as a tool for representing algorithms and programming logic but had extended to use in all other kinds of processes. Nowadays, flowcharts play an extremely important role in displaying information and assisting reasoning. They help us visualize complex processes, or make explicit the structure of problems and tasks. A flowchart can also be used to define a process or project to be implemented.

Fig 3: Flowchart

3.3 STATE CHART DIAGRAM:

State chart diagram is one of the five UML diagrams used to model the dynamic nature of a system. They define different states of an object during its lifetime and these states are changed by events. State chart diagrams are useful to model the reactive systems. Reactive systems can be defined as a system that responds to external or internal events.

State chart diagram describes the flow of control from one state to another state. States are defined as a condition in which an object exists and it changes when some event is triggered. The most important purpose of State chart diagram is to model lifetime of an object from creation to termination.

Fig 4: State Chart Diagram

Here is a description of a state chart diagram for a simplified malware recognition system:

Initial State: The system is in the initial state when it is ready to receive a dataset sample for classification.

Sample Received: When a software sample is received, the system transitions to the "Sample Received" state. It triggers the feature extraction process and moves to the "Feature Extraction" state.

Feature Extraction: In this state, the system extracts relevant features from the software sample. Once the feature extraction is complete, the system transitions to the "Feature Extraction Complete" state.

Model Classification: In the "Feature Extraction Complete" state, the system applies the trained machine learning model to classify the software sample as either malware or benign. It transitions to the "Model Classification Complete" state.

Classification Result: The system provides the classification result to the user or external system in the "Model Classification Complete" state. It can transition back to the "Initial State" to receive the next software sample or wait for further instructions.

4. IMPLEMENTATION

Project implementation is the process of putting a project plan into action to produce the deliverables, otherwise known as the products or services, for clients or stakeholders.

Implementation of our project include following:

- Installation of Python in the system.
- Methodology Used.
- Source Code.

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Upload Test Data And detect attack. Where Malware is detected and predicted.

Fig 5: Upload Test

Accuracy graph of both SVM and ANN algorithm

Fig 6: Accuracy Test

6. SYSTEM TESTING

The purpose of testing is to discover errors. Testing is the process of trying to discover every conceivable fault or weakness in a work product. It provides a way to check the functionality of components, sub-assemblies, assemblies and or a finished product It is the process of exercising software with the intent of ensuring that the

Software system meets its requirements and user expectations and does not fail in an unacceptable manner. There are various types of tests. Each test type addresses a specific testing requirement.

6.1 TESTING METHODOLOGIES:

The following are the Testing Methodologies:

- Unit Testing.
- Integration Testing.
- User Acceptance Testing.
- Output Testing.
- Validation Testing.

6.2 Test cases

Sl. No.	Description	Input	Expected Result	Status
1.	Choose Dataset	Network Dataset	CSV dataset	Correct Result
2.	Pre process	Network Dataset	Cleaning data	Correct Result
3.	Training	Network dataset	SVM Module	Correct Working
4.	Training	Network dataset	ANN Module	Correct Working
1.	Test Dataset	Test CSV file	ANN Module	Correct Result
2.	Comparison	Test Dataset	ANN and SVM	Correct Result

7. CONCLUSION

To obtain relatively higher classification accuracy by using the common machine learning algorithms, a complicated procedure of feature engineering is necessary to select and extract the most useful features from the huge feature space.

Based on the machine learning techniques, the determination of feature selected, size of feature space, input representation methods exert impacts on classifiers performance more or less, and it costs great efforts on making comparisons and conducting experiments to make the best decision. The proposed system using ANN algorithm predicts higher accuracy compared to SVM algorithms, which involves several key components and considerations. By following a systematic methodology, it is possible to develop a robust and effective machine learning based malware recognition system that can contribute to enhancing cyber security differences protecting against malicious software threats.

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